

EFFECT OF BUCKLES MESOSCOPIC DEFECTS ON THE COMPOSITE PROPERTIES

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Keywords: Defects, Buckles, Forming processes, Composite

ABSTRACT

The aim of this study is to evaluate the effect of the "buckles" mesoscopic defects on the composites mechanical properties. For this purpose, an analysis was made on the kinematics involved during the appearance of these defects on complex shapes. Then, a device and a protocol were developed in order to realize calibrated specimens. "Buckles" defects have been generated on interlock dry fabric layers taking care to reproduce the amplitudes observed on a complex composite part used for aeronautical application. Composites plates with four stacked layers were then injected and specimens were cut in different areas before mechanically testing them under uniaxial tensile. The results of tensile tests showed that the "buckles" defects have no or little effect on the elastic parameters of the material. Indeed, even if these mesoscopic defects have an effect, the significant contribution of the transverse yarn to the mechanical behavior has not allowed highlighting the influence for these mesoscopic defects. However, the SEM observations made on the broken specimens surfaces resulted in highlight showed the presence of damage in the case of the specimens with calibrated defects.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fibre reinforced polymer composites are increasingly used in engineering applications due to their high specific stiffness. Additionally, the current energy crisis places the composites materials as an essential solution to design lightweight structures, especially for transportation industries.

To manufacture these parts, forming processes (LCM, Thermoforming, etc....) are among the most used candidates. The quality of the obtained shape with these processes plays a crucial role on the mechanical performances of the final composite part. Indeed, preforming step is a delicate phase that could lead to various defects which are harmful to the final composite behaviour. Therefore, the knowledge of the criticality of these defects on the composite properties will permit to consider different industrialization strategies, depending on the application, function of the acceptable quality of the composite part that can be also defined with different levels. For example, for high-end applications only parts without defects can be accepted while for other applications, where the final price must be lowest as possible, parts with defects can be accepted knowing the criticality of their effect.

Defects that appear during textiles forming processes can be divided in two types: macroscopic and mesoscopic (Figure 1). Macroscopic defects take place at the fabric scale. Among the defects that occur during textile reinforcement forming process, wrinkles are the most common and widely studied ones in the literature. It has been shown that wrinkles are highly dependent on the fabric behaviours and the boundary conditions. The first studies have limited the relationship between the limits of the mechanical behaviour reached during the process and wrinkles to the link between the

in-plane shear behaviour and this macroscopic defect. This aspect is described by numerical and experimental approaches and focalized on values of the shear angle reached during the process comparatively to the locking angle [1-4]. Recently, numerical studies [5-7] have shown that the membrane behaviour must be completed by the bending behaviour in order to describe correctly the wrinkle shape and sizes, because it's an out-of-plane phenomenon. A coupling between shear and tension has been highlighted in different papers [8-10] and wrinkles can, therefore, be avoided or delayed by applying tension along the yarn's networks. Besides, wrinkles do not depend only of the in-plane shear behaviour but are the results of all strains and rigidities of the fabric (tension, in-plane shear, bending) and to the boundary conditions [10]. Wrinkles defects, appearing at the reinforcement scale, generate significant over thickness that has an effect on the geometrical tolerances and aesthetics of the final part. Furthermore, studies have shown that this defect lead to a significant decrease of the composite performance, reaching up to 40% loss of failure strength [11-13], what is completely unacceptable.

Figure 1: Defects observed on double curved shape: (a) macroscopic, (b) and (c) Mesoscopic defects.

The second kind of defects, that are mesoscopic defects, appears at the yarn level. Among these defects, there may be mentioned fibres and/or yarn breakage, "buckles", "weave pattern heterogeneity", "yarn waviness", etc.... Some of these defects were only recently identified. Indeed, except some work on the phenomena involved in the defects like "yarn waviness", "buckles", and "weave pattern heterogeneity" on some phenomena involved during their appearance, there are few studies treating of the mesoscopic defects [10, 14-16]. Concerning the effect of mesoscopic defects, except some studies on the effect of the fibre waviness on the UD composite [17-19], there are no studies to our knowledge on this subject. However, it has been shown that they are more recurring during complex preforms shaping [6, 10]. In addition, the inter-ply sliding increases significantly the amount and extent of these defects when multi-layered composite shaping is concerned [20], hence the need of understanding the phenomena involving and their criticality on the obtained composite.

This study is therefore in this framework and aims to evaluate the effect of the "buckles" defect on the composites mechanical properties. For this, "buckles" have been generated on interlock dry fabric layers (G1151®) taking care to reproduce the amplitudes observed on a complex composite part used for aeronautical application (figure1). Composite plates, of four stacked layers at the same orientation, were then performed by injecting epoxy resin using RTM device. Plates without defects were also fabricated to be used as a reference. Observations were made during injection in order to evaluate quantitatively the effect of the defect on this step. Thereafter, uniaxial tensile tests, instrumented with optical and acoustic measurements devices, were performed. Results of these tests were compared in order to evaluate the effect of "buckles" on the tensile behaviour of the composite and the damage mechanisms.

2 MESOSCOPIC DEFECTS

This study deals with the "buckle" mesoscopic defect that appears at the yarn level. This defect appears when the yarns are submitted to buckling out of plane of the fabric (Figure 2). This leads locally to a significant overthickness that can achieve several times the initial thickness of the fabric. For example, for the case of only one layer of G1151 interlock, this overthickness reaches 5 mm, while the fabric thickness is only about 0.62 mm. Therefore this defect may be a cause for disposal of

composite parts after their manufacturing for geometric non-compliance. In addition, this defect may have an effect on the behavior of the obtained composite hence the need to evaluate its criticality and understand the involved mechanisms in order to develop shaping strategies for achieving healthy preforms. To achieve this purpose, this study proposes to evaluate the effect of this defect by performing mechanical tests on calibrated specimens.

Figure 2: “buckles” mesoscopic defect.

To realize these specimens, the kinematics of the apparition of the “buckles” was identified on preforming tests done on done on tetrahedron punch (Figure 3). Figure 3 shows that this defect appears on a tape with a width of about 3cm located at the center of the face. This area is delimited with two zones where the shear angles are in the same order of magnitude (here 24°), but that occur in two opposite directions: clockwise and counterclockwise [6, 10]. On the defect area, one network of yarns (here in blue) are curved, while the yarns of the other network (in red) remain straight and are submitted to a large tension due to severe geometry of the top of the punch which is a triple point. To conclude we can say that the triple point apply a tension on the straight yarns that carry with them the transverse yarns (due to the fabric cohesion) inducing the two shear areas and also the bending of the yarns in blue and as a consequence their out of plane buckling. This kinematic, will therefore be used to reproduce calibrated specimens.

Figure 3: Tetrahedron preform realized with interlock dry fabric.

3 MESOSCOPIC DEFECTS SPECIMENS PREPARATION AND CHARACTERIZATION

The kinematics described in the previous section was used to produce calibrated specimens with “buckles” mesoscopic defects. After cutting the fabric fold, a displacement was imposed (in y direction) on some yarns of one network that are in the center of the ply while the fabric is guided in translation at its two lateral ends (Figure 4). After validating this principle, an experimental device was

designed and built. An experimental protocol was also established and allows realizing calibrated specimens like the one illustrated on figure 4 where the mesoscopic defect is obtained vertically at the center of the specimen.

Figure 4: Calibrated specimen realized with one ply of G1151® interlock fabric.

The fabric used in this study is interlock woven fabric denoted G1151®. It's produced by the Hexcel Company and constituted by an interlock weaving of 6 K carbon yarns. Its nominal construction is 7.5 yarns/cm for warp and 7.4 yarns/cm for weft and the areal weight is 630 g/m². For the realization of the calibrated specimens, several calibrated plies of the interlock fabric were made according to the protocol described previously. These plies have been made so as to reproduce as faithfully as possible the observed state of buckles "defects" during previous studies dealing with the feasibility of complex parts for aeronautical application [10]. Thus, each ply was realized separately with a shear angle of the lateral areas of about 40±2° which leads to a defects zone of a width between 2cm and 3cm.

Thereafter, a laminates of 4 plies with the same orientation (0°) were performed and then inserted in a VARTM mold before injecting an epoxy resin (LY564/XB3487 Huntsman) at a pressure of 6bars. All precautions have been taken in order to have plates without porosities. Healthy plates without defects were also realized in order to use their testing results as a reference. The final composite plates obtained have an average thickness of 3 mm and a fiber content of about 50%.

Test specimens were subsequently cut on the injected composite plates to test them mechanically. These specimens were divided into three batches according to their origin. The first group is that of healthy specimens cut on the reference plates. The second batch, denoted A, was obtained on the sheared regions of the plates with calibrated defects ((Figure 4). The third group, noted B, consists of specimens cut from the area with the "buckles" defects ((Figure 4). Subsequently uniaxial tensile tests with optical measurements were carried out on these samples and the results are presented in the next section.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results of the uni-axial tests permit to measure mechanical parameters of the different batches of specimens which are presented on figure 5. The results show that the Young modulus and maximal stress values of the healthy specimens are lower than the other batches (A and B). The maximal values for the two parameters were obtained for the specimens "A" that were cut at the sheared area of the plates. This is due to the contribution of the transverse yarns to the behavior in the tested direction. For healthy specimens, only the yarns of the network that is in the tested direction contribute to the

composite stiffness. As for specimens of the batch “A” the fabric is sheared, the yarns of the transverse network provide additional stiffness. This contribution can also be assessed using the laminate theory. The mechanical parameters of the specimens of batch “B” that contain “buckles” defects are higher than the healthy specimens and lower than the specimens “B”. The same explanation as previously can be given. Indeed, in the defect area the transverse yarns are curved (see figure 3), and thus the shear decreases symmetrically to either side from the values of the neighboring areas to achieve zero at top of the yarns curvature. Consequently, this leads to a lower contribution of the yarns of the transverse network on the composite stiffness.

Figure 5: Mechanical parameters of the tested composite specimens.

Figure 6: Loading/unloading tensile test performed on specimens with “buckles” defects (batch B)

We can therefore conclude that the "buckle" defects have no, or little, significant effect on the elastic parameters. Indeed, even if these mesoscopic defects have an effect, the contribution of the transverse yarns on the elastic parameters is significant and prevented highlighting the influence of the “buckles”. Considering the fact that the “buckles” defects appear at the mesoscopic level, it can be expected that their effect will be more visible on the cyclic behavior and the damage of the composite material. To assess this assumption, uniaxial tests with loading/unloading were performed on specimens of the batch “B”. Figure 6 present an example of the obtained force/displacement curve. We note a mechanical behavior containing a hysteresis effect during unloading. This can be due to a damage phenomenon of the composite. To check this fact, SEM observations were made on broken faces of specimens of the different batches.

Figure 7: SEM observations: a. Healthy specimens; b. specimen with “buckles” (batch B).

The observations made on healthy specimens with a small magnification we have noted a clean broken surface that include a longitudinal yarns broken combined broken fiber/matrix debonding. For the specimens with "buckles" defects, the facies is not clear and we have also observed broken transverse yarns. By increasing the magnification these observations were confirmed. For the case of healthy specimens, the longitudinal fibers sharply and cleanly break without debonding with the matrix (Figure 7.a). In the other hand, specimens with “buckles” defects showed between the longitudinal fibers and the matrix, denoting the presence of diffuse damage of the composite (Figure 7.b). This damage should have an effect by reducing the stiffness of the composite in contrast to the positive contribution of transverse yarns previously observed. Further tests and investigations are needed to evaluate the combined effect of the damage and the contribution of the transverse yarns and the share of each of them on the overall behavior of the composite material.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Effect of draping defects on the mechanical properties of composite materials is a major challenge for the development of the use of composites in different technological fields. The aim of this work is to contribute to the understanding of the effect of “buckles” mesoscopic defects that are recurrent when dealing with preforming of complex shapes. To achieve this aim, a device was designed and built in order to produce calibrated specimens with defects that have the same amplitude that those observed during a study concerning the feasibility of an aeronautical part. After validating the device, a protocol was established and specimens were realized with VARTM process.

The results of uniaxial tensile tests showed that the "buckles" defects have no or little effect on the elastic parameters of the material. Indeed, even if these mesoscopic defects have an effect, the significant contribution of the transverse yarn to the mechanical behavior has not allowed highlighting the influence for these mesoscopic defects. However, the SEM observations made on the broken specimens surfaces resulted in highlight showed the presence of damage in the case of the specimens with calibrated defects.

Future work will focused on the effect of the “buckles” defects on the injection stage and in quantifying the material damage under fatigue testing. The mechanisms involved in the appearance of the mesoscopic defects will be, in turn, studied in order to propose and develop industrial strategies to obtain composite parts with acceptable quality.

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